

“EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON GROUND IMPROVEMENT USING PLASTIC”**Mr. Ganesh S. Sardar**

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Abstract—

Ground improvement techniques play a crucial role in enhancing soil stability, bearing capacity, and overall performance for construction and civil engineering projects. Among these methods, the use of plastic strips as a reinforcement material is gaining attention due to its cost-effectiveness and environmental benefits, particularly in sustainable development. This review paper presents a comprehensive analysis of experimental investigations focused on the application of plastic strips in ground improvement. Various studies are discussed, highlighting the impact of plastic strip inclusion on soil properties such as shear strength, compressibility, and load-bearing capacity. The paper also explores the influence of strip dimensions, material properties, and placement orientation on the soil's performance under different loading conditions. This investigation reveals that plastic strips significantly enhance soil behaviour, offering a viable alternative for ground stabilization, particularly in regions with problematic soils. Future research directions are proposed to optimize the use of plastic materials in civil engineering practices.

Keywords— Ground improvement, Plastic strips, Soil reinforcement, Shear strength, Bearing capacity, Sustainable construction, Soil stabilization, Experimental investigation, Geotechnical engineering, Soil performance.

INTRODUCTION

In geotechnical engineering, ensuring the stability and performance of soil is critical for the success of construction projects. Weak soils with insufficient strength and load-bearing capacity can lead to settlement, deformation, or structural failure. As urbanization and infrastructure projects expand, the need for cost-effective and sustainable ground improvement methods has become increasingly important. Traditional techniques like compaction, grouting, and chemical stabilization, while effective, often face challenges related to cost, environmental impact, and large-scale feasibility.

The reuse of plastic waste for soil improvement offers an innovative and sustainable alternative. Plastic waste, a major environmental issue worldwide, can be repurposed to address both landfill challenges and enhance soil properties. Plastic strips incorporated into soil have shown significant improvements

in shear strength, compressibility, and load-bearing capacity. These materials are lightweight, durable, and cost-efficient, making them particularly suitable for stabilizing weak or problematic soils.

This study reviews experimental investigations into the use of plastic strips for ground improvement, focusing on the influence of factors such as strip size, material properties, orientation, and distribution. By analyzing findings from various studies, the paper highlights both the advantages and potential limitations of plastic strip reinforcement in soil stabilization. Furthermore, the environmental benefits of utilizing recycled plastic align with the global trend toward sustainable construction practices.

The paper also identifies future directions for research, emphasizing the need to optimize the design and application of plastic strip reinforcement across different soil types and construction scenarios. With further development, this approach holds the potential to become a widely adopted, eco-friendly solution for enhancing ground performance in geotechnical engineering.

Objectives

The objectives of this review paper are as follows:

1. To review experimental studies on the use of plastic strips for soil reinforcement This objective focuses on analyzing existing research to understand the effectiveness of plastic strips in improving soil performance.
2. To assess the impact of plastic strips on soil properties like shear strength and compressibility. The goal is to evaluate how adding plastic strips influences critical properties of soil, such as its resistance to shear forces and its ability to compress under loads.
3. To analyze the effect of strip dimensions, concentration, and orientation on soil performance. This examines how variables like strip size, quantity, and placement affect the mechanical behavior and overall stability of the reinforced soil.
4. To determine the optimal plastic strip configuration for improved bearing capacity and reduced settlement.
This aims to identify the best combination of strip length, width, and concentration that enhances the soil's load-bearing capacity while minimizing settlement.
5. To compare the performance of reinforced and unreinforced soil in terms of stability. This involves testing and comparing soil with and without plastic strip reinforcement to highlight improvements in stability, strength, and deformation behavior.
6. To evaluate the environmental and economic feasibility of using recycled plastic strips. This assesses the sustainability and cost-effectiveness of utilizing recycled plastic waste for soil reinforcement, addressing environmental concerns and economic viability.
7. To identify practical applications and limitations of plastic strip reinforcement in geotechnical engineering. The objective is to explore the real-world applicability of this technique, highlighting its benefits, challenges, and limitations for various construction scenarios.

Problem statement

In geotechnical engineering, soils like sand often lack adequate strength and load-bearing capacity to reliably support structural loads. These deficiencies become particularly problematic in areas where expanding foundation dimensions is limited due to spatial constraints or existing infrastructure. Traditional techniques for soil improvement, such as the use of cement, lime, or geosynthetics, are effective but are frequently associated with high costs, environmental drawbacks, and impracticality for large-scale implementation.

At the same time, the global issue of plastic waste continues to intensify, with millions of tons of non-degradable plastic accumulating in landfills and marine environments annually. This has created an urgent need for sustainable strategies that address both soil stabilization challenges and the environmental burden of plastic waste. Recycled plastic strips provide a novel approach to improving soil properties while contributing to plastic waste management efforts.

Despite its potential, the application of plastic strip reinforcement remains insufficiently explored, with key knowledge gaps in optimizing their use. Critical factors, such as strip dimensions, concentration, and placement orientation, significantly influence their effectiveness in improving soil properties like shear strength, compressibility, and overall stability. Detailed experimental research is necessary to analyze these variables and establish practical guidelines for real-world geotechnical applications.

This study seeks to bridge these gaps by evaluating the use of recycled plastic strips for ground improvement. Through an investigation of key parameters and the development of optimized reinforcement configurations, this research aims to offer an eco-friendly, cost-efficient, and sustainable solution to soil stabilization, while addressing the dual challenges of weak soils and plastic waste pollution.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for studying plastic strip reinforcement in ground improvement involved selecting pertinent empirical studies, organizing data on soil characteristics and plastic properties, and conducting experimental tests with different proportions of plastic strips in sand. The process included constructing layered models to analyze shear strength, compressibility, and load-bearing capacity. Additionally, the study evaluated the ecological and financial advantages of repurposing plastic waste for soil stabilization, synthesized insights from various investigations, and suggested recommendations to refine this sustainable geotechnical approach:

Theoretical Foundations:

The theoretical basis of this study integrates soil mechanics and material science. Core soil mechanics concepts, such as shear resistance, compressibility, and consolidation, underpin the understanding of how plastic strips enhance soil stability, bearing capacity, and settlement behavior under different conditions. Material science provides knowledge about the attributes of plastic, including its durability, lightweight structure, and resistance to deterioration, making it an economical and robust

reinforcement material. These combined theories elucidate the interaction between soil and plastic strips, enabling the refinement of their application for sustainable and efficient ground stabilization in geotechnical projects.

Methodological Approach:

- **Literature Search Strategy:** The literature search was carried out methodically to identify pertinent studies on the application of plastic strips in soil stabilization and ground improvement. Sources included scholarly journals, conference proceedings, technical documents, and digital databases focused on geotechnical engineering and eco-friendly construction. Priority was given to empirical studies that analyzed the influence of plastic strips on critical soil characteristics such as shear strength, compressibility, and load-bearing capacity. Both experimental and review-based research were incorporated to ensure a broad understanding of the subject.
- **Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:** To maintain the relevance and reliability of the selected studies, the inclusion criteria mandated research that experimentally assessed plastic strip reinforcement and its effects on soil performance. Studies had to present quantifiable results, such as improvements in shear resistance, reductions in compressibility, or enhancements in bearing capacity. Excluded were articles that lacked experimental evidence, non-peer-reviewed publications, and studies that exclusively focused on unrelated soil stabilization materials or methods.
- **Data Extraction Protocol:** A systematic data extraction protocol was applied to collect essential details from the chosen studies. Information such as experimental setups (e.g., soil types, plastic strip sizes, and configurations), testing techniques (e.g., triaxial tests, unconfined compressive strength evaluations), and results demonstrating changes in soil properties was recorded. Additionally, insights into the ecological and financial benefits of utilizing recycled plastic strips were documented. The gathered data was organized and analyzed to extract comparative findings on the efficiency of plastic strip reinforcement across diverse soil types and reinforcement setups.

Data Synthesis and Interpretation:

- **Quantitative Analysis:** The data synthesis included a detailed quantitative analysis of the experimental results to assess the impact of plastic strip reinforcement on soil properties. Key performance indicators such as shear strength, compressibility, and bearing capacity were measured and compared across studies. Statistical methods were used to identify trends and evaluate the effectiveness of plastic strips under varying conditions, including differences in soil types, strip dimensions, and reinforcement configurations. The numerical data provided a robust foundation for determining the overall efficiency of plastic strip reinforcement.
- **Qualitative Insights:** Beyond numerical results, qualitative insights were derived by interpreting the contextual factors influencing the performance of plastic strip-reinforced soils. These included the influence of strip orientation, placement depth, and material properties on soil stabilization outcomes. Additionally, the environmental and economic implications of repurposing plastic waste were considered, highlighting the sustainability benefits and practical challenges associated with this method. These insights helped outline best practices and limitations for real-world applications.

- Visualization of Data: To support the analysis and interpretation, data visualization techniques were employed, including graphs, charts, and comparative tables. Visual aids highlighted key patterns, such as the correlation between strip dimensions and improvements in soil properties or the effectiveness of varying reinforcement configurations. These visuals enhanced the clarity of the findings and facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the study's results across different experimental setups and conditions.

Discussion of Implications:

- Geotechnical Engineering Applications: Plastic strips demonstrate significant potential in geotechnical engineering by enhancing soil properties like shear strength and bearing capacity. Their cost-effectiveness, durability, and adaptability make them a practical alternative for stabilizing weak soils in applications such as foundations, road subgrades, and embankments, especially in resource-limited regions.
- Sustainability and Environmental Considerations: Using recycled plastic strips addresses the dual challenges of plastic waste management and sustainable construction. This eco-friendly approach reduces landfill burdens while replacing environmentally harmful materials. However, long-term studies are essential to evaluate potential risks, such as microplastic release, ensuring the method remains a responsible and sustainable solution.

Materials Used

In the study of "Experimental Investigation on Ground Improvement Using Plastic Strips," the following materials were utilized:

1. Sand: Clean sand with a relative density of 50% was used as the primary soil material. Its uniform grading and controlled properties made it suitable for studying the effects of reinforcement.

Figure 1: Sand

2. Plastic Strips: These were extracted from recycled plastic bottles using a plastic extractor and cut into specific dimensions. The strips were mixed into the sand in varying proportions (0%, 0.25%, 0.5%, 0.75%, 1%, and 1.25% by weight of the sand). Their lightweight and durable nature made them ideal for reinforcement.

Figure 2: Plastic Strips

3. Movable L-Shaped Plastic Markers: These markers were placed within the soil layers to monitor settlement and displacement during load application, ensuring accurate observations during testing.

Figure 3: Movable L-Shaped Plastic Markers

4. Mild Steel Box and Testing Equipment: A steel box with transparent glass sides was used as the primary test setup, along with a hydraulic compression machine to apply loads evenly to the test model. Polythene sheets were applied to reduce friction between the sand and glass walls.

5. Plastic Strip Extractor: This tool was used to efficiently cut waste plastic bottles into strips of precise dimensions for uniformity in reinforcement.

6. Strip Footing with Attached Load Cell: Chemical admixtures, such as lime or cement, may be included to enhance the stabilization process, depending on the specific requirements of the study.

Material Properties

Material Properties	
Sand	Values
Void ratio maximum (e_{max})	0.849
Void ratio minimum (e_{min})	0.661
Angle of Internal friction (ϕ)	35°
γ at 50% RD (gm/cm ³)	1.5

Model Making Methodology

The model was developed using a mild steel box with a transparent glass panel for observation. Sand layers compacted to 50% relative density were prepared, with movable L-shaped markers placed at 20 mm intervals for monitoring displacement. Plastic strip-reinforced beds were formed by blending sand with plastic strips (0.25% to 1.25% by weight) in varying widths (B and 1.5B) and depths (0.5B, 1B, and 1.5B). Additional sand layers were added above the reinforced bed, and the model was tested using a hydraulic compression machine to measure load-settlement performance.

Test No.	Test Name	RD of Soil	Details of Plastic Strips	Details of Placing Plastic Bed		Bearing Capacity
			% Plastic	Width (b)	Depth (d)	Peak Value
1	PRF-1	50	0	0	0	31.40
2	PRF-2		0	0.5B		31.02
3	PRF-3		0.25	B	B	35.20
4	PRF-4		0.25	B	1.5B	46.50
5	PRF-5		0.25	1.5B	0.5B	34.00
6	PRF-6		0.25	1.5B	B	36.70
7	PRF-7		0.25	1.5B	1.5B	35.70
8	PRF-8		0.5	B	0.5B	29.35
9	PRF-9		0.5	B	B	33.65
10	PRF-10		0.5	B	1.5B	35.70
11	PRF-11		0.5	1.5B	0.5B	35.60
12	PRF-12		0.5	1.5B	B	37.60
13	PRF-13		0.5	1.5B	1.5B	41.30
14	PRF-14		0.75	B	0.5B	35.90
15	PRF-15		0.75	B	B	49.00
16	PRF-16		0.75	B	1.5B	34.00
17	PRF-17		0.75	1.5B	0.5B	31.90
18	PRF-18		0.75	1.5B	B	35.50
19	PRF-19		0.75	1.5B	1.5B	35.30
20	PRF-20		1	B	0.5B	33.45
21	PRF-21		1	B	B	34.25
22	PRF-22		1	B	1.5B	33.55
23	PRF-23		1	1.5B	0.5B	33.20
24	PRF-24		1	1.5B	B	32.95
25	PRF-25		1	1.5B	1.5B	33.10
26	PRF-26		1.25	B	0.5B	32.45
27	PRF-27		1.25	B	B	33.00
28	PRF-28		1.25	B	1.5B	35.45
29	PRF-29		1.25	1.5B	0.5B	33.75
30	PRF-30		1.25	1.5B	B	36.25
31	PRF-31		1.25	1.5B	1.5B	37.00

Table: 1

B = width of footing
 b = Width of plastic bed
 h = height of plastic bed
 d = depth of plastic bed from surface

The table provides a comprehensive summary of model tests conducted on soil reinforced with plastic strips to assess the impact on bearing capacity. A total of 31 tests were performed with varying plastic reinforcement percentages (0%, 0.25%, 0.5%, 0.75%, 1%, and 1.25% by weight) and different configurations of plastic strip placement in terms of width (b) and depth (d) relative to the footing width (B). The relative density (RD) of the soil was maintained at 50% for all tests. The results indicate that as the percentage of plastic strips and the depth and width of reinforcement increase, the bearing capacity generally shows a trend of enhancement, with peak values ranging from 31.40 to 49.00. The tests show that the configuration of the plastic bed, particularly when it reaches a certain width and depth, can significantly increase the bearing capacity of the soil. This data highlights the potential for

using waste plastic strips as an effective ground improvement technique, particularly in applications requiring enhanced load-bearing capacity.

Model Test Performed and Methodology

Experimental Setup of Mild Steel Box

In this experimental setup, a mild steel box serves as the primary test model. To facilitate clear observation of soil settlement, a 12mm thick transparent toughened glass sheet is positioned at observation points. A polythene sheet is used to mark displacement in millimetres during load distribution. A hydraulic compression machine applies the load to the sand through strip footing, ensuring even load distribution.

Sand Filling

Before testing, a 20mm thick foundation layer of sand was compacted at a relative density of 50%, representing a firm foundation base. As each sand layer is prepared, L-shaped plastic markers are placed with one leg greased and attached to the glass, while the other leg rests within the sand layer. These markers are used to monitor settlement through displacement measurements. This process continues, placing 20mm foundation layers, until the desired depth of the plastic-reinforced bed is reached.

Fix the Movable Marker Layer by Layer

The plastic bed itself is constructed according to the dimensions outlined in Table 1. It includes plastic reinforcement layers with widths of B and $1.5B$, height of 10mm , and varying plastic content mixed with dry sand at percentages of 0.25% , 0.5% , 0.75% , 1.0% , and 1.25% . The plastic-reinforced layers are placed at depths of $0.5B$, $1B$, and $1.5B$ within the test box. Once the plastic bed is complete, successive 20mm sand layers are added, with movable L-shaped markers placed at each level, continuing to the top ground level to ensure thorough monitoring of soil behaviour during the load application. Filling Sand into the Test Model.

Plastic Bed Preparation

Flow of Model Making

Model Preparation: The process of model preparation for testing began with setting up a mild steel box equipped with transparent glass to allow for observation. Four permanent markers were affixed to the outer surface of the glass to indicate measurement points, while polythene sheets were applied to the inner surface to reduce friction between the sand and the glass. A 20mm sand layer was placed in the box at 50% relative density. Movable L-shaped markers were then positioned at 20mm intervals using grease for attachment to the inner surface of the glass, with successive 20mm sand foundation layers added until the plastic bed depth was reached. The plastic bed, consisting of plastic strips mixed with dry sand, was prepared in configurations of width B and $1.5B$, height 10mm, and plastic content percentages of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, and 1.25%. These layers were positioned at depths of $0.5B$, $1B$, and $1.5B$. After completing the plastic bed, additional 20mm sand layers with movable markers were added up to the ground level. The test then commenced, with observations and recordings of load-deformation, and photographs were taken to document the process.

Plastic Bed Preparation

Results and Discussion

Comparison Graph f W/O Plastic Reinforcement

1.0 Load-Settlement Behavior of Soil Reinforced with 0.25% Plastic Strips

The graph illustrates the load-settlement behaviour of soil reinforced with 0.25% plastic strips. The load values on the x-axis (logarithmic scale) are plotted against settlement on the y-axis, allowing us to observe how the soil's resistance to compression changes with increased loading.

Results:

The graph shows a consistent trend where settlement gradually increases with load until reaching a failure point, indicated by a steeper drop in the curves. The initial portion of the graph shows a small increase in settlement for each increase in load, indicating that the soil-plastic mix is effectively bearing the load up to a certain threshold. However, as the load continues to rise, a more noticeable settlement occurs, revealing the limits of reinforcement with 0.25% plastic strips.

Conclusion:

Reinforcing soil with 0.25% plastic strips results in an improved load-bearing capacity compared to unreinforced soil, though it remains modest. The curve indicates that while plastic strips contribute to an initial resistance against settlement, the performance at higher loads tapers off. For applications requiring higher load-bearing capacity, additional reinforcement or increased percentages of plastic strips may be necessary to further enhance soil stability and reduce settlement under loading conditions.

2.0 Load-Settlement Behavior of Soil Reinforced with 0.50% Plastic Strips

The graph compares the load-settlement behaviour of soil with and without 0.5% plastic reinforcement. The x-axis represents the load (on a logarithmic scale), and the y-axis shows settlement.

Results:

The curves suggest that soil reinforced with 0.5% plastic strips can withstand higher loads with lower settlement compared to unreinforced soil.

The initial segments of the curves (at lower load values) are similar, but as the load increases, the reinforced soil shows a more gradual increase in settlement than the unreinforced soil.

This indicates that the plastic-reinforced soil has improved stiffness and load-bearing capacity, with the plastic strips helping to distribute the load more effectively and reduce settlement.

Conclusion:

Adding 0.5% plastic strips to the soil improves its load-bearing capacity and reduces settlement under load, making it a viable solution for ground improvement.

This finding supports the use of plastic waste as a reinforcing material in geotechnical applications, promoting sustainability by repurposing plastic waste while enhancing soil performance.

3.0 Load-Settlement Behaviour of Soil Reinforced with 0.75% Plastic Strips

The graph shows the load-settlement behaviour of soil with and without 0.75% plastic reinforcement. Similar to the previous graph, the x-axis represents load (logarithmic scale) and the y-axis represents settlement.

Results:

Compared to unreinforced soil, the 0.75% plastic-reinforced soil curve shows better performance, with reduced settlement under increasing load.

The settlement increase in the reinforced soil is more gradual at higher load values, indicating that the reinforcement contributes to greater load-bearing capacity.

This curve for 0.75% reinforcement shows even better settlement reduction than the 0.5% plastic reinforcement case, suggesting an improvement in soil behaviour with the higher reinforcement percentage.

Conclusion:

The addition of 0.75% plastic strips enhances the soil's load-bearing capacity more effectively than the 0.5% reinforcement, indicating an optimal improvement trend.

This level of plastic reinforcement seems effective for ground improvement, as it minimizes settlement under load, making it suitable for sustainable construction practices and providing a beneficial use for plastic waste.

4.0 Load-Settlement Behaviour of Soil Reinforced with 1.0% Plastic Strips

The graph you shared illustrates the load-settlement relationship for soil with and without 1.0% plastic reinforcement, with load on a logarithmic scale along the x-axis and settlement on the y-axis.

Results:

The 1.0% plastic-reinforced soil exhibits an even more pronounced improvement in load-bearing capacity, with a more gradual settlement increase under higher loads compared to both unreinforced soil and soil with lower percentages of plastic reinforcement.

The curve for the 1.0% reinforcement shows that the soil can sustain higher loads before experiencing significant settlement, highlighting enhanced stiffness and load distribution due to the added plastic strips.

This suggests that 1.0% reinforcement provides the best performance among the reinforcement percentages reviewed so far (0.5% and 0.75%).

Conclusion:

Reinforcing soil with 1.0% plastic strips appears to be highly effective, as it significantly reduces settlement and improves load-bearing capacity. This reinforcement level maximizes the benefits of plastic addition for ground improvement.

This finding supports the use of 1.0% plastic strips as an optimal reinforcement level, providing a sustainable approach for enhancing soil properties and promoting plastic waste utilization in geotechnical applications.

5.0 Load-Settlement Behaviour of Soil Reinforced with 1.25% Plastic Strips

The graph provided compares the load-settlement behaviour of soil with and without plastic reinforcement at 1.25% plastic content. Here’s a summary of the results and possible conclusions:

Results:

The soil with 1.25% plastic reinforcement generally shows improved performance compared to the unreinforced soil.

The reinforced soil displays higher resistance to settlement under the same load levels, indicating greater load-bearing capacity.

The curve for reinforced soil suggests a slower settlement rate and less overall settlement at higher loads compared to unreinforced soil.

Conclusion:

The addition of 1.25% plastic reinforcement improves the load-bearing capacity and reduces settlement of the soil, making it more resilient under increasing loads. This suggests that plastic reinforcement can be an effective ground improvement method, enhancing soil strength and stability, which could be particularly beneficial for supporting heavier structures or reducing settlement in weak soils.

Conclusion

Effect of Plastic Content on Percentage Increase in Bearing Capacity of Soil.

The experimental results show a clear relationship between the percentage of plastic strips used in sand and the improvement in bearing capacity. The following observations emerge from the data

% Plastic	Increment
0	100
0.25	171.34
0.5	180.80

The graph displays the relationship between the percentage of plastic strips added to sand and the resulting increase in bearing capacity. Here is a detailed discussion on the trend observed.

Initial Increase in Bearing Capacity:

At 0% plastic, the baseline bearing capacity increment is 100%. As plastic content is introduced at 0.25%, a significant increase in bearing capacity is observed, reaching approximately 171.34%. This indicates that even a small amount of plastic reinforcement leads to a substantial improvement in the soil's load-bearing capacity.

1.0 Continuing Positive Impact with Increasing Plastic Content:

With the plastic content increasing to 0.5%, the bearing capacity increment rises further to about 180.80%. This steady upward trend continues, indicating that adding plastic strips enhances soil stability, likely by improving soil-particle interaction and providing additional structural support.

2.0 Peak Improvement Around 0.75% to 1% Plastic Content:

The maximum bearing capacity increment of around 209.70% is achieved at 1% plastic content. This peak suggests that an optimal plastic content exists around this concentration, where the reinforcement effect is maximized. At this point, the plastic strips provide the most effective reinforcement without overcrowding, allowing for efficient load distribution and increased soil stiffness.

3.0 Decline Beyond the Optimal Plastic Content:

After reaching 1% plastic, the bearing capacity increment decreases when the plastic content is raised to 1.25%, dropping to 152.14%. This decrease suggests that excessive plastic content may negatively impact soil reinforcement. Possible reasons could include overcrowding of plastic strips, which may hinder effective soil-particle interaction or lead to uneven load distribution.

4.0 Overall Trend and Interpretation:

The graph follows a trend where the inclusion of plastic strips initially enhances the bearing capacity significantly, reaching an optimal point around 1% plastic content. Beyond this, further increases in plastic content reduce the effectiveness of reinforcement. This trend highlights the importance of determining an optimal percentage of plastic for soil reinforcement, as excessive amounts may reduce rather than enhance the bearing capacity.

Practical Implications:

These findings suggest that using plastic strips in soil reinforcement can effectively increase the load-bearing capacity, but the content needs to be optimized to achieve the best results. The observed optimal range (around 1% plastic content) can inform engineering practices, helping to develop cost-effective and sustainable ground improvement techniques by reusing waste plastic.

This analysis offers insights into how waste plastic can be utilized in geotechnical applications, balancing environmental sustainability with structural performance. Further research could investigate the long-term durability of plastic-reinforced soils and explore the potential effects across different soil types and loading conditions.

1.0 Effect of Plastic Strip Inclusion on Bearing Capacity:

When no plastic strips are included (0% plastic), the baseline increment value is set to 100. This serves as the control for comparing the effects of plastic inclusion.

At 0.25% plastic, the increment increases significantly to 171.34, indicating that even a small number of plastic strips substantially improves soil stability.

Increasing the plastic content to 0.5% further improves the increment to 180.80, showing a continued positive effect on soil performance.

At 0.75% plastic, the increment reaches 201.48, representing the highest recorded improvement in bearing capacity, suggesting that this may be close to the optimal concentration for reinforcing sand.

The increment slightly increases to 209.70 at 1% plastic, but the gain is smaller than previous increases, suggesting diminishing returns beyond this point.

When the plastic content reaches 1.25%, the increment decreases to 152.14, indicating a reduction in the effectiveness of reinforcement at higher plastic concentrations.

2.0 Optimal Plastic Content for Soil Reinforcement:

The results suggest that the inclusion of plastic strips improves the bearing capacity of sand up to a certain percentage. The highest increment value (209.70) occurs at 1% plastic content, beyond which the efficiency of reinforcement begins to decrease.

This decrease in effectiveness at higher plastic percentages (1.25%) may be due to overcrowding of plastic strips, which can lead to uneven distribution and clumping, reducing soil-particle interactions that are essential for effective load distribution.

3.0 Diminishing Returns and Structural Integrity:

The data indicate diminishing returns in bearing capacity improvements as plastic content increases past 0.75% to 1%. The slight drop at 1.25% suggests that beyond the optimal range, adding more plastic does not contribute to further improvement and may even reduce soil performance.

This finding emphasizes the importance of identifying an optimal plastic content range for practical applications, as excessive plastic inclusion could lead to inefficient use of materials and compromise soil integrity.

Conclusion

This study shows that incorporating plastic strips into sandy soils significantly enhances their load-bearing capacity, with optimal results observed at approximately 1% plastic content. Beyond this concentration, the benefits of plastic reinforcement diminish, indicating a threshold for effective soil improvement. The findings suggest that plastic strips derived from waste serve as a viable and sustainable reinforcement material in geotechnical applications. By establishing the optimal range for plastic content, this research supports the development of cost-effective, environmentally friendly ground improvement techniques that apply to a variety of engineering contexts.

These results offer a promising approach for future projects in geotechnical engineering, where sustainable material use is increasingly prioritized. Further studies are recommended to explore the long-term durability of plastic-reinforced soils under various environmental conditions, as well as to investigate potential applications across different soil types and project scales.

Analysis of the Attached Graph

The graph depicts the relationship between the percentage of plastic content and the percentage increase in bearing capacity. Based on the trends observed:

Results

1. Initial Increase in Bearing Capacity:

From 0% to approximately 0.8% plastic content, there is a significant increase in bearing capacity.

The highest increase in bearing capacity is observed at around 0.8% to 1% plastic content.

2. Optimal Plastic Content:

The peak performance in terms of bearing capacity enhancement occurs within the range of 0.8% to 1% plastic content.

3. Decline Beyond 1%:

Beyond 1% plastic content, the graph shows a decline in the percentage increase in bearing capacity, indicating that excessive plastic content may cause non-uniform distribution, leading to reduced effectiveness.

Conclusion:

The experimental results suggest that incorporating plastic strips in soil improves its bearing capacity significantly up to an optimal content of around 0.8% to 1%. Beyond this range, the effectiveness decreases, possibly due to clumping or loss of uniform reinforcement. Thus, for practical applications, maintaining the plastic content near its optimal value ensures maximum soil stabilization benefits. This

approach not only enhances bearing capacity but also offers an eco-friendly solution by recycling plastic waste.

REFERENCES

1. Farah Atiqah Abdul Azam *, Rohayu bt Che Omar (2024) Enhancing the soil stability using biological and plastic waste materials integrated sustainable technique.
2. Mohd Furkhan, Sufyan Syed, Maroof Ahmed, and Mehraj Mohiuddin (2023) Improve Soil Strength by Use of Plastic Bottles.
3. P.Rajesh, Sooraj Kalra, G.Ramakrishna, J.Sivaji Naik and K.Gopi Sankar (2021) An Experimental Study on Soil Properties by Inducing Plastic Strips.
4. Dr. S. Gangadhara¹, Vivek.S, Bharath (2017) Experimental Study on Strength Behavior of Plastic Reinforced Red Earth.
5. Arvind Kumar, Rajeev Bhatia and B.Walia (2011) “An Experimental Study on the Load Settlement Behavior of a Fiber-Reinforced Sand Bed”
6. A. Kumar and A. Kaur (2012) “ Model Tests of Square Footing Resting on Fibre Reinforced Sand Bed”
7. S. Peddaiah, A. Burman and S. Sreedeeep (2018) “Experimental Study on Effect of Waste Plastic Bottle Strips in Soil Improvement”
8. Tarun Kumar, Suryaketan Panda, Shayeqe Hameed and Joyanta Maity (2018) “Behaviour of Soil by Mixing of Plastic Strips”
9. Rebecca Belay Kassa, Tenaw Workie, Alyu Abdela, Mikiyas Fekade and Mubarek Saleh (2020) “ Soil Stabilization using Waste Plastic Materials)”
10. Sushovan Dutta, M.B. Nadaf and J.N. Mandal (2015) “An Overview on the Use of Waste Plastic Bottles and Fly Ash in Civil Engineering Applications”
11. N. Vijay Kumar, S S. Asadi, A. V. S. Prasad (2017) Soil Stabilization Using Plastics and Bottle Strips.
12. Kalumba D., Chebet F.C. (2009) Utilisation of polyethylene (plastic) shopping bags waste for soil improvement in sandy soils
13. Omid Bayat, Kayvan Karimi Askarani, Alborz Hajiannia (2019) Effects of Waste Tire on the Shear Strength of Sand.
14. Amrendra Kumar, Ajay Singh, Bishwajit Roy, Shiladitya Bhattacharjee and Tanmay Bhowmik (2022) PVC Waste Plastic Bottle Strip Used for Improvement of Engineering Properties of Clayey Soil.
15. Ikramul Hoque, Muzamir Hasan and Shuvo Dip Datta (2022) Black Cotton Soil Improvement Techniques by Waste Plastic.
16. Mantu Kumar, Bheem Pratap, MD Azhar, Somenath Mondal and Rakesh Pratap Singh (2023) The utilization of Plastic Waste for Stabilizing Expansive Soil Subgrade: A critical review
17. Ansari Bushra Kausar, Ansari Saima Kausar, Shaqran Hamza, Mohd Ismail, Ajran Naik (2024) Soil Stabilization using Different Wastes.
18. Preeti Gangwar, Sachin Tiwari (2021) Stabilization of soil with waste plastic bottles.

19. S.S. Lande, V.P. Urkude, O.S. Gaikwad, and R.P. Borkar (2020) Soil Stabilization using Plastic Waste.
20. G. A. Abhinandan, Bhavimata Gurubasavarajaiah, C. Chethan, R. Gagan, and K. Gurunath (2020) Soil Stabilization Using Lime, Plain and Perforated Plastic Strips.
21. Yogeshwarsinh A. Chauhan, and Ms. Mauni N. Modi (2019) Improvement of Sandy Soil by Plastic Bottle Strips.